

Urban Sanitation problems and Challenges in Karnataka: An Overview

Asha T¹, Dr. S. N. Yogish²

¹Research Scholar, ²Professor and Chairman

Department of PG Studies and Research in Economics,

Kuvempu University, JnanaSahyadri, Shankaraghatta, Shivamogga, Karnataka, India

ABSTRACT

Urban sanitation is the very important role of creation well known smart cities. In Indian context the people should give more preference to maintain a good sanitation the history study proved particularly the urban sanitation problems main issue in 12st century. The focuses on identification analysis and sanitation problems and challenges and paper based on purely secondary sources of information.

Keywords: *Sanitation, Challenges, Problems, Issues, and Impacts.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The seriousness of the challenges associated with urban sanitations in India has been recognized in recent times. After de 3cades of neglect the first national effect to invest in the urban sanitation sector commenced in the 1970s but was accorded considerable priority in the subsequent two decades as a part of different national and state schemes culminating most of the Swatch Bharat Mission. As most of the recent reports and comment arises have highlighted the problems of the urban sanitation sector in India.

The present paper attempts to highlight the urban sanitation problems and challenges while the concerns of urban sanitation are faced in many countries and states. According to the 2011 census India has a total population of 1.21 billion which an addition of 181 million people during the decade of 2001-2011 (census of Indian 2016).

Although only 31.16 per cent of India is urban according to the census of India at 37 million India's current urban population is large than the entire population of United States which is the third most populous country in the world.

1.1 Meaning of Sanitation

Sanitation is the effective use of tool action that keep our environment healthy. These include latrines or toilets to waste food preparation washing stations, effective drainage and other such mechanisms.

2. Review of Literature

Zimmer Manm (2006), compared investment reinvestment and during costs of potential sanitation system in Syria over a period of 30 years. His results show that UDDTs or constructed wetlands could be E5-20, cheaper per inhabitant and year than oxidation dishes.

Mohamed (2006), the UDDTs alternative remains undoubtedly cheaper than constructed wetland as long as the number of served inhabitants is below 50000 more information on costs of waste water treatment.

Heranmi (2006),examined six sanitation concepts for an area in a newly planned settlement in Nigeria designated for 600 in habitants.The results of his least cost analysis indicate the cheapest systems are low or pour flush toilets with onsite Rottebehaelter treatment.

3. ResearchGap

There are number of research papers related to vision of a sanitation problems and challenges but there is no particular study related to urban and selection process and present study focused on sanitation problems and challenges. So the study is attempted.

4. Objectives of the Study

The present study was undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To identify and analyze the sanitation problems and challenges.
2. To study the sanitation issues and impacts.

5. Methodology

The present study on secondary source of information gathered from the urban satiation journal articles, newspapers and relevant websites etc.

6. Analysis and Interpretation

The identify the sanitation problems in urban area.

- Lack of proper sanitation facilities increase the environmental problems particularly during rainy season.
- Over flowing soat pits contaminate water and soil and also affect the health of people in urban areas.
- The problem gets worsened in low lying areas, where usually poor people live.
- Siltation, blocking of soiled waste and damage in the sewage.

7. Issues and Impacts

- Sanitation issues in urban areas include lack of latrine and underground drainage facilities.
- Only 36 urban local bodies, except Bangalore and the city municipal councils around Bengaluru have been covered with underground drainage facilities.
- Even in those town where the underground drainage is being provided the percentage
- Coverage of the households is relatively less.
- The 182 urban local bodies are yet to provide with underground drainage system in the state.
- Most of the urban local bodies do not have sewage treatment plants to treat waste water.
- For instance, out of 36 urban local bodies, where underground drainage system is provided 9 urbanlocal bodies do not have treatment plants.

8. Sanitation Challenges

➤ Growing Population

The growing population increases the demand for domestic use, food security and industrial development.

➤ Water Scarcity

Water is currently limited to an annual fresh water supply in this regard. Therefore, Karnataka is classified as a water scarce state.

➤ ClimateVariability and Water Resources Degradation

Drought is recurrent and its impact on water resources is usually devastating.Both climate variability and environmental degradation have resulted into

- a. Catchment degradation
- b. Drying up of rivers

➤ Storage and Infrastructure Investment

The storage capacity has been low due to the fact that investment level in water management infrastructure was on a declining trend for many years. Catchment has reduced groundwater recharge and storage.

➤ Climate Change

The earth surfacetemperature as well as the amount, timing and intensity of precipitation including storms and droughts. Climate change is expected toexacerbate pressure directly or indirectly on all aquatic ecosystems.

➤ Catchment Degradation

The main cause of catchment degradation are poor farming methods. Population pressure and deforestation, catchment degradation.

9. Suggestions

- Prepare slum action plan for implementing slum up gradation programmer at each slum level.
- Rehabitate the low lying slum in the city prone for inundation to an alternate environment friendly site.
- Educate or conduct awareness programmes to both women and men to control the solid waste dumping into open drains.

- Public taps to every lane in the slum though exclusive waste connection with timely and regular water supply needs to be provided.
- All the storm water drains to be desalted and maintained properly.

Conclusion

Sanitation its give more important to development to aspect. In India the government should give preference to cleanness in the name of Swatch Bharat Mission etc. However, every people should take care of the maintenance of the good sanitation systems so friendly urban.

References

- 1) **International Water Association .2008**,10Things you should know about sanitation21.WorldHealth Organization, London.
- 2) IHSRE paper on Urban Water Supply and Sanitation in India.
- 3) Joint Monitoring programme. 2012,**Progress on Drinking Water and Sanitation**. World health organization, Washington Dc.
- 4) Peal, A.and B. Evans. 2011,**Breaking Barriers in Water Sanitation Services and Delivery to Informal Settlements: Case Study of Mukuru Model**, Nairobi. Practical Action, Kenya.